

Passive Filler Loaded Polysilazane-Derived Glass/Ceramic Coating Systems

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ABSTRACT

This study describes the development of a corrosion resistant environmental barrier coatings on AISI 441 stainless steel substrates. For that purpose, double layer polymer derived ceramic (PDC) coating systems consisting of a bond coat and a top coat were developed. In order to achieve well adherent coatings without failures, stainless steel substrates were cleaned by four different cleaning procedures, such as ultrasonic vibration cleaning in acetone, ethanol and deionised water, sandblasting with glass beads, chemical etching with Kroll's reagent and combination of these methods. The pre-treated substrates were then dip-coated in perhydropolysilazane (PHPS) solution to obtain bond coat. The pyrolysis of the bond-coat was performed in air at a temperature of 450 °C for 1 h. The subsequently applied top coat was prepared by mixing defined volume fractions of a liquid polysilazane HTT1800, ceramic filler particles (yttria-stabilized zirconia – YSZ, Al₂O₃-Y₂O₃-ZrO₂ powder - AYZ), and commercial glass frits (G018-281, Schott AG). The resulting mixture was applied by spray-coating technique. Parameters like the volume fraction of the HTT1800 polymer, filler and glass system were varied in order to optimise the coating systems. All coated samples were heat treated in air at 850°C for 1 h. The selected optimised compositions are listed in Tab.1.

Tab. 1: Compositions of the composite top coats before pyrolysis (vol. %)

	HTT1800	YSZ	G018-281	AYZ
D1	20	20	40	20
D2	25	20	35	20
D3	30	20	30	20

The surface morphology of pre-treated steel samples was examined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and roughness parameters were observed using atomic force microscope (AFM) and Raman spectroscopy. The results showed that chemical etching results in a surface with irregular morphology, while this treatment led to the slight roughening of the surface ($R_z = 0.88 \mu\text{m}$) compared to ultrasonically cleaned substrates ($R_z = 0.27 \mu\text{m}$). More uniform and compacted surface was achieved by the sandblasting with glass beads, while the average surface roughness R_z increased to a value of $1.70 \mu\text{m}$.

To investigate the bonding between the bond coat and steel substrate treated by different cleaning procedures, cross sections of the composition D2 were prepared for SEM examination (Fig.1). The chemical etching with the Kroll's reagent caused considerable changes in the microstructure and the chemistry of stainless steel and as a result, the bond coat peeled off the substrate. In the case of sandblasted samples, the sharp borders and peaks initiated the formation of cracks and spallation of bond coat in the coatings. On the other side, pre-treatment by ultrasonic

cleaning in acetone, ethanol and deionised water was found to be the most effective. In order to clarify the bonding between the coating and steel, the selected coatings were tested under prolonged static exposure for 24 hours in air at 850 °C. After heat treatment, all coatings, except for those applied to ultrasonically cleaned substrates, delaminated or significant cracking was observed in the bond coat.

Fig. 1: SEM cross-sectional micrographs of the coating D2 applied to pre-treated steel substrates: a) ultrasonic cleaning, b) chemical etching, c) sandblasting, d) sandblasting + chemical etching

After a thermal treatment in air at 850 °C, the resultant coating applied to ultrasonically cleaned substrates with the thickness up to 40 µm is almost fully dense, with no cracking or delamination and it is expected to prevent the access of aggressive environment to the steel substrate at elevated temperatures. Additionally, this microstructure system with residual porosity is beneficial to the thermal stability of the coatings, as it contributes to the reduction of the thermal stresses during heating and cooling cycles. These results confirmed that the combination of PDC with tailored fillers and glass systems enable the processing of dense and crack free coating systems.

Keywords: bond coat, PDC coating, stainless steel

Acknowledgment:

This paper is a part of dissemination activities of project [FunGlass](#). This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 739566.